

D2.3

Dashboard report

Version 2
May 2025

D2.3/Dashboard report

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Abstract

This report presents the development and implementation of the MYRIAD-EU dashboard, built around the MYRIAD-EU framework aimed at advancing systemic, multi-hazard, and cross-sectoral disaster risk management (DRM) across Europe. The dashboard consolidates tools, guidance protocols, data, and case studies from across the project into a user-friendly, accessible platform designed to support risk managers, decision-makers, and researchers. Developed through a collaborative, iterative process involving all work packages and pilot regions, the dashboard provides tailored support for implementing the MYRIAD-EU Framework and Multi-Risk Pathways approach. It serves both as an operational tool and a legacy resource, enabling integrated risk assessment and management by offering scenario modelling tools, storylines, a serious game, and open-source software. By facilitating access to practical methodologies and dynamic data, the dashboard strengthens multi-risk understanding and supports long-term decision-making. This report details the dashboard's objectives, structure, development milestones, and future outlook, highlighting its role in sustaining MYRIAD-EU's impact beyond the project's duration.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Reviewers	Description
V1	09/05/2025	Authored by Stephanie Brookes (Arctik), Emma Cabascia (Arctik), Agnieszka Pietruczuk (Arctik) Stefan Hochrainer-Stigler (IIASA). Reviewed by Philip Ward (VUA), Adrian Champion (Aon)	Version submitted to Quality Unit for internal review
V2	20/05/2025	Authored by Stephanie Brookes (Arctik), Emma Cabascia (Arctik), Agnieszka Pietruczuk (Arctik) Stefan Hochrainer-Stigler (IIASA). Reviewed by Philip Ward (VUA), Adrian Champion (Aon)	Version submitted to European Commission

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1. Introduction

1.1. Context of the MYRIAD-EU dashboard and its role in the MYRIAD-EU framework

Task 2.3, focused on dashboard development, is a core component of WP2, whose overall aim is to develop a harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, systemic risk management (see Deliverable 2.1, Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2022). The framework provides a set of guidance protocols for multi-hazard, multi-risk assessment and management which were updated four times over the lifetime of MYRIAD-EU, tested and refined through implementation in the Pilots in WP3 in an iterative process informed by feedback from Pilot core users and stakeholder groups. Those included stakeholders from the public and private sector, e.g. the EUSDR Danube Strategy Point in the Danube Pilot, the The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency for the Scandinavia Pilot, the Internal Waters Observatory Service in the Veneto Region, ASHOTEL for the Canary Pilot (for more details we refer to Deliverable 3.1).

The MYRIAD-EU framework addresses the increasing complexity and interconnectedness of natural hazards in Europe (see Deliverable 2.1 (Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2022) and Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023). It promotes a systemic, multi-risk, and cross-sectoral approach to disaster risk management (DRM) by providing a set of practical guidelines for carrying out a multi-risk assessment, formalised in guidance protocols. By integrating diverse methodologies, data, and stakeholder insights, it supports coherent and informed decision-making. The dashboard consolidates the various products and services from across MYRIAD-EU (see Figure 1) into a user-friendly platform. It is supported by guidance protocols that provide clear, accessible instructions tailored to different users.

Figure 1: Vision, overall aim and products and services of MYRIAD-EU

In more detail, the [MYRIAD-EU dashboard](#) is designed to facilitate navigation of the framework. It contains products and services from within and outside MYRIAD-EU (Figure 1). The dashboard functions both as an operational tool and a legacy platform, offering stakeholders streamlined access to the harmonised risk management framework co-developed across five pilot regions: the North Sea, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, Danube, and Veneto. Beyond serving as a technical interface, the dashboard recognises that advancing natural hazard risk science requires more than models alone, and it therefore is structured according to a step-by-step process with guidance protocols that support the navigation through each step.

1.2. Objectives of the dashboard

The overall aim of the dashboard is to help risk managers, decision-makers and researchers to navigate through the MYRIAD-EU framework. In doing so, the dashboard offers clear and accessible ways forward that help users navigate the complex nature of multi-hazard, multi-risk, and systemic risk to apply integrated approaches in real-world contexts. In addition, the dashboard is intended as a long-term support tool that will maintain the relevance and usability of MYRIAD-EU's results beyond the duration of the project (up to 5 years after the project ends). Through the possibility of providing ongoing updates and the integration of new resources, tools, and case studies, it will continue to provide various stakeholders involved in disaster risk management with access to practical guidance, methodologies, and examples of good practice in multi-risk management until the projects end. After that project ends, the work package leads and the pilot regions will also be provided with back-office access to the platform with the possibility to update data and information.

1.3. Target users

The dashboard is designed to support risk managers, decision-makers, and researchers in navigating and applying the MYRIAD-EU framework. It serves both project participants and external stakeholders, offering access to a wide range of tools and resources. The overarching aim is to encourage these target audiences not only to use the dashboard's content in their own work, but also to actively promote its adoption and integration into broader disaster risk management practices.

2. Dashboard development

2.1. Development timeline and key milestones

The development of the MYRIAD-EU dashboard follows an iterative and collaborative approach. The process began in June 2022 and continues through to May 2025, with the dashboard being progressively populated and refined over time. It was a very resource intensive task as all WPs had to be actively involved to provide input, feedback as well as several iterations for integration across the WPs. The need for extended development stemmed from the importance of understanding stakeholder needs, particularly within the Pilots. A dedicated session was held during the April 2022 General Assembly to gather input from across WPs. In addition, many new figures had to be created to increase the understanding of the main concepts as well as to include the comments and suggestions from the Pilots within the dashboard. On average, there was at least 1 meeting per month for some detailed discussions on each step for the single WPs, with some additional meetings on a bi-weekly basis to discuss figures and processes that need to be included for each step. Every 2-3 months some broader meetings across the WPs were held to provide the necessary integration of the different themes within the overall framework. Between August 2022 and February 2023, six scoping and brainstorming meetings took place, allowing the consortium to agree on the content, structure, functionalities, and visual identity of the dashboard. The first visual mock-ups appeared in January 2023, and a password-protected version was shared in February 2023. From a broad-based perspective the key development milestones include:

- Initial design and planning (June-August 2022): Establishment of dashboard architecture and user interface design, led by Arctik in collaboration with IIASA, VUA, and other partners.
- First release (September 2022): Launch of the first online version of the dashboard with initial resources, including early guidance documents and foundational tools.
- Progressive integration (October 2022-August 2024): Ongoing updates to include tools, datasets, pilot case studies, guidance protocols, and external project links. User testing and feedback are incorporated to refine functionality and usability. Nine structured meetings were held between Arctik and the WPs to define content, visuals, and integration points, resulting in a clearer, more intuitive interface aligned with the MYRIAD-EU framework.
- Final release and legacy strategy (August 2024-December 2025): Consolidation of content, including the full suite of products and services, storylines, serious game, and interactive components. The public release of the dashboard took place in July 2024, with major sections including 'About MYRIAD-EU', 'Assessment and

Management’, ‘Resources’, and ‘Themes’, which collectively reflect the structure of the framework. The dashboard content continues to be updated and expanded. Future additions will include Pilot region pages, additional storylines, and an online serious game.

Throughout its development, the dashboard has been shaped by feedback from project partners and external stakeholders, ensuring it remains responsive, user-friendly, and relevant. Its design reflects a commitment to accessibility, clarity, and the promotion of systemic risk understanding across sectors.

2.2. Structure of the dashboard

We do not go into the technical details of the architecture of the dashboard and back-end development (which was considerable) but just want to note that already at an early stage the architecture focused on the different steps of the framework that had to be performed in an iterative fashion for analysing multi-hazard and multi-risks within a systemic perspective. Accordingly, the pages on the dashboard are specified in the following sections:

- Assessment and management:
 - a. Framework

The MYRIAD-EU framework (see Figure 2) offers a flexible, collaborative approach to managing complex multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. It consists of six iterative steps—from defining the system to evaluating risks and planning for future changes—each supported by tailored tools and methods. These tools help users assess direct and indirect risks, explore management options, and integrate future projections into decision-making. Within the dashboard, each step from the overall framework can be clicked on and a new window is opened which explains the overall concepts used within the framework. This also includes some conceptual examples to bring the main messages across as well as detailed guidelines (through the guidance protocols) on how to perform each step. In addition, the various resources produced by MYRIAD-EU can be viewed and links are provided to indicate which tools are available to be used. Finally, for each step the link to the Pilot Case studies is provided, where each step was performed and explained in detail.

Figure 2. MYRIAD-EU six-step framework for carrying out multi-hazard, multi-sector, and systemic risk analysis

b. Multi-Risk Pathways

Within the MYRIAD-EU Framework the future system state (step 6) was expanded to include detailed information about the Multi-Risk Pathways approach. The MYRIAD-EU Multi-Risk Pathways approach provides a structured method for designing adaptive disaster risk management strategies in complex, interconnected environments. Known as Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR), this approach helps navigate uncertainty by sequencing risk management measures over time (see Figure 3). Through a staged, iterative process, it identifies how sector-specific measures interact and influence each other, revealing synergies and trade-offs. Supported by qualitative and quantitative tools—such as storylines, scenario modelling, and pathway mapping—DAPP-MR complements the MYRIAD-EU Framework and enables the formulation of flexible, forward-looking risk reduction plans.

Figure 3: The DAPP-MR process to formulating multi-risk pathways

- Pilots

The five MYRIAD-EU pilot regions—Canary Islands, Veneto, Scandinavia, North Sea, and Danube—serve as real-world laboratories to test and refine the project's multi-risk, cross-sectoral framework. Each pilot has a dedicated section on the Dashboard, reflects distinct regional challenges and priorities and follows the structure and iterative steps of the MYRIAD-EU framework to guide their risk assessments and planning. Together, these pilots demonstrate how integrated, forward-looking disaster risk management strategies can be tailored to diverse regional contexts, informing policy and practice across Europe. Within the dashboard, one section is dedicated to the five Pilots and detailed information is given on the work performed under each step of the framework, including which tools and methods have been used and main results.

- Resources

- a. *Disaster Risk Gateway*

The [Disaster Risk Gateway](#) is an open-access, collaborative wiki to support the discovery and sharing of resources for understanding, analysing, and managing multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. Designed for researchers, practitioners, policymakers, educators, and students, it serves as a growing catalogue of platforms, frameworks, models, tools, and definitions relevant to disaster risk management. The Disaster Risk Gateway encourages contributions from the broader risk community and aims to encourage transparency, co-creation, and accessibility of knowledge.

- b. *Terminology and Concepts*

The MYRIAD-EU Handbook provides a foundational reference for multi-hazard and multi-risk terminology, offering a shared language to support interdisciplinary disaster risk management. Drawing on internationally recognised glossaries and enriched by project-specific insights, the handbook presents a glossary of 140 terms, six key sector descriptions, and three types of hazard interrelationships. It proposes draft indicators for multi-risk characterisation, preparedness, and governance, and outlines a roadmap for their future application (see Figure 4). Through key reflections on terminology use, evolving definitions, and the importance of viewing risk through a multi-hazard lens, the handbook strengthens conceptual alignment across sectors and underpins the MYRIAD-EU Disaster Risk Gateway.

Figure 4: The MYRIAD-EU Handbook and its 6 sectors descriptions

c. Storylines to support multi-risk decision-making

The storylines approach supports multi-risk decision-making by using narratives of past or plausible future events to explore and characterise the cause-and-effect relationships between risk drivers and impacts within a system. Emphasising plausibility over probability, storylines help unpack cause-and-effect relationships and examine how changes in system elements—or decisions made—could alter the trajectory of multi-hazard events (see Figure 5). They support holistic, often qualitative analyses that account for uncertainty and non-quantifiable factors. Applied by MYRIAD-EU pilot teams, storylines help build the understanding of complex multi-hazard risks, facilitate cross-sectoral stakeholder engagement, communicate systemic interconnections to raise awareness, and support the development of forward-looking decision-making pathways.

Multi-hazard risk storyline elements

Figure 5: Multi-hazard risk storyline elements to support multi-risk decision making

d. Storylines repository

The Storylines Repository showcases multi-risk narratives developed by MYRIAD-EU pilot regions to explore how diverse hazards interact and affect regional systems. Each storyline—visualised through ArcGIS StoryMaps—illustrates the unique multi-hazard dynamics of a given region, supporting stakeholder dialogue and cross-sectoral planning. By examining both historical events and plausible future scenarios these storylines help characterise risk drivers, encourage shared understanding, and inform the co-creation of adaptive disaster risk management strategies.

- Themes

a. Multi-Risk Dynamics

The Multi-Risk Dynamics theme investigates how interactions between multiple hazards and risk drivers—such as exposure and vulnerability—evolve over time and space. Combining traditional and novel methods like machine learning, disaster forensics, satellite data, and qualitative interviews, this work builds an evidence base to improve understanding of cascading, compound, and consecutive hazard events. Key outputs include a growing database of 100+ multi-hazard case studies, the *VulneraCity* urban vulnerability database (Stolte et al., 2024), and tools for mapping multi-hazard susceptibility and evaluating risk management performance. These insights are integrated into the MYRIAD-EU dashboard to inform risk modelling, scenario development, and forward-looking disaster preparedness strategies for decision-making and risk management strategies.

b. Multi-Risk Scenarios

The Multi-Risk Scenarios theme includes software tools to simulate multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios across Europe. These tools integrate exposure metrics—such as

population, infrastructure, agriculture, and economic activity—to assess the potential impacts of hazards like earthquakes, floods, wildfires, and volcanic eruptions. By extending single-hazard data into a multi-hazard context and developing vulnerability models, the tools support both large-scale and localised risk estimation. A web-based Scorecard enables users to assess disaster risk management performance, helping identify critical hazard combinations and their effects. These tools are being applied in pilot regions to deliver a flexible, practical approach to forward-looking risk assessment.

c. Risk-Informed Decision-Making

The Risk-Informed Decision-Making theme advances practical tools and methods to support adaptive, system-wide disaster risk management. At its core is a collaborative systems analysis approach that enables stakeholders to co-define systems, identify key risks and interdependencies, and explore trade-offs across sectors. A central component is the Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways for Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR) approach, an expanded version of the MYRIAD-EU Framework that guides iterative, integrated risk analysis to inform the development of long-term Multi-Risk Pathways. A Storyline approach is used to explore past and potential future multi-risk events to qualitatively implement systems and risk analyses and pathways formulation.

3. Next steps

As MYRIAD-EU moves towards its final phase, a major focus will be on ensuring the long-term visibility, uptake, and impact of the dashboard and associated project outputs. A targeted communication and dissemination campaign will be launched to promote the dashboard widely, positioning it as an accessible, user-friendly entry point for multi-hazard and multi-risk management.

Further efforts will include:

- **Finalising the Dashboard** by completing it with the serious game, the software and storylines repository.
- **Extending the dashboard's visibility** through a targeted marketing communication campaign. The campaign will be designed to promote widespread adoption of the MYRIAD-EU dashboard by crafting compelling, sector-relevant messages that highlight its practical value in multi-risk decision-making. The campaign will target government and public agencies—including decision-makers and policymakers at national, regional, and local levels—as well as researchers, academic institutions, and risk planners. By leveraging tailored outreach and a mix of communication channels and tools (organic social media campaigns, communication toolkit, webnews, newsletter) the campaign aims to ensure the dashboard reaches its intended audiences, generates interest, encourages active use, and gains visibility among harder-to-reach stakeholders.
- **Actively looking for funding** through other Horizon projects to support Dashboard operations after the project ends.

The MYRIAD-EU project will continue until the end of December 2025. In the remaining months, efforts will focus on further improving the dashboard and enhancing its usability, and promoting it more widely to target audiences. Project partners will be given access to

the backend of the dashboard, enabling them to update, complete, or refine the content directly.

Looking ahead, the dashboard will be kept online for at least five years beyond the end of the project, ensuring continued access to its tools, resources, and guidance. While Arctik will not provide ongoing technical maintenance, the consortium is committed to seeking new opportunities to finance further development and support through future projects. Where possible, we will aim to integrate the dashboard into new initiatives, ensuring it remains a dynamic, evolving platform that continues to advance multi-risk management across Europe and beyond.

4. References

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